

A new species of the genus *Stauropoctonus* Brauns (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Ophioninae) from India

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Abstract

The genus *Stauropoctonus* Brauns, is recorded for the first time from India with a new species *S. narendrani*. Description of new species with illustrations, key to the Oriental species of *Stauropoctonus* and affinities to the related species are also included.

Keywords: *Ophioninae, Stauropoctonus, New species, Key, Oriental, India.*

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Introduction

The genus *Stauropoctonus* Brauns, 1889 is a small group belonging to the Subfamily Ophioninae and family Ichneumonidae of Order Hymenoptera. It comprises of 11 described species and is distributed in the Afrotropical, Australian, Neotropical, Oriental and Palaearctic regions (Gauld and Mitchell, 1981; Lima *et al.*, 2013; Yu *et al.*, 2016). In Oriental region, three species have been previously recorded viz., *S. bombycivorus* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *S. torresi* Gauld, 1977 and *S. townesorum* Gauld and Mitchell, 1981. The members of this genus *Stauropoctonus* can be easily recognized by the presence of following characteristics: presence of transverse mesopleural furrow and the mid and hind trochantelli with distal margins each produced into a sharp curved tooth (Gauld, 1985, 1988). Although little is known about the biology of genus *Stauropoctonus*, it is assumed that they are solitary endoparasitoids of lepidopterous larvae with some host records of large lepidopteran species like notodontid lobster moth (Uchida, 1928, 1951; Gauld and Mitchell, 1981). In this paper, the genus *Stauropoctonus* is recorded for the first time from India with the description of a new species. A key to the Oriental species of *Stauropoctonus* and the affinities of the new species with the closely related Oriental

species of *S. bombycivorus* (Gravenhorst) and the Japanese species *S. infuscus* (Uchida) are also discussed.

Materials and Methods

The specimen was collected using light trap from Kannavam forest in Kannur district, Kerala. The collected specimen was then dried, pinned using entomological pin and the morphology of specimen was examined under Leica M205 stereozoom microscope. The image was captured using Leica DMC 2900 digital camera attached. Measurements were obtained using Leica LAS (Leica Application Suite) microsystem and the final illustrations were post processed for contrast and brightness using Adobe Photoshop CS5 software. This study is based on a single female specimen, and due to the rarity of this genus, further attempts did not yield any additional material. The type specimen is deposited in the collection of Prof. T.C. Narendran Biodiversity Research Laboratory, The Zamorin's Guruvayurappan College, Kozhikode (NBRL).

Morphological terminology, abbreviations and indices

Morphological terminology follows Gauld and Mitchell (1981) and Gauld (1991). The indices used in this paper follows Gauld

and Mitchell (1981), Lima *et al.* (2013) and Shimizu and Mateo (2016) and Shimizu and Lima (2018).

Abbreviations used: HL = head length; HW = head width; FWL = fore wing length; FWW = fore wing width; HWL = hind wing length; HWW = hind wing width; S = metasomal sternite; T = metasomal tergite.

Indices for head

FI (Frontal Index) = maximum diameter of median ocellus / distance between eyes;

GOI (Geno-orbital index) = maximum breadth of eye in profile/ maximum breadth of gena in same line.

Indices for wing

AI (Alar Index) = length of 1m-cu between 2m-cu and bulla/ length of 3rs-m;

CI (Cubital Index) = length of Cu1 between 1m-cu and Cu1a/ length of Cu1b;

DI (Discoidal Index) = maximum vertical distance between Cu1a and 1m-cu/ length of Cu1a between Cu1b and 2m-cu;

ICI (Intercubital Index) = length of 3rs-m/ length of M between 2m-cu and 3rs-m;

SDI (Second Discoidal Index) = length of Cu1a between Cu1b and 2m-cu/ length of Cu1 between Rs+M and 1m-cu;

SI (Sinuous Index) = maximum length between 1m-cu and a straight line connecting the intersection of M, 2m-cu and 1m-cu and the intersection of 1m-cu and Cu1/ distance between the intersection of M, 2m-cu and 1m-cu and the intersection of 1m-cu and Cu1;

SRI (Second Recurrent Index) = Index of 2m-cu/ length of Cu1a between Cu1b and 2m-cu;

NI (Nervellar Index) = length of Cu1 between M and cu-a/ length of cu-a.

Indices for metasoma

DMI (Dorsal Metasomal Index) = length of dorsum of T2/ length of dorsum of T3;

LMI (Lateral Metasomal Index) = length of dorsum of T2/ posterior depth of T2;

PI (Petiolar Index) = distance between base of T1 and anterior margin of spiracle/ distance between margin of spiracle and apex of T1.

Results

Systematic Status

Family: Ichneumonidae

Subfamily: Ophioninae

Tribe: Ophionini

Genus: *Stauropoctonus*

Genus *Stauropoctonus* Brauns, 1889

Stauropoctonus Brauns, 1889: 75. Type-species: *Ophion bombycivorus* Gravenhorst, by monotypy.

Stauropodoctonus Morley, 1913: 375. (Unjustified emendation).

Nipponophion Uchida, 1928: 201. Type-species: (*Nipponophion variegatus* Uchida) = *Stauropoctonus bombycivorus* Gravenhorst, by original designation.

Diagnosis: Mandible twisted with two subequal tooth; clypeus in profile weakly convex; occipital carina absent; antennae with 56-76 flagellomeres; scutellum weakly convex with lateral longitudinal carinae; posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete; epicnemial carina present, its upper end not reaching anterior margin of mesopleuron; mesopleural furrow well developed, extending from episternal scrobe to upper angulation of epicnemial carina; anterior transverse carina on propodeum complete; fore tibial spur without trace of membranous flange behind microtrichial comb; distal margin of mid and hind trochantelli produced into an acute curved tooth; forewing with 1m-cu sinuous; discosubmarginal cell with a glabrous area in anterior corner, without detached sclerites; hindwing with first abscissa of Rs almost straight; vein R1 with 3-13 hamuli of similar size and shape.

Distribution: Australia, China, Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Japan, Korea, Norway, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Brunei, Indonesia, Malaysia, Papua New Guinea. First record from India.

Key to the Oriental species of *Stauropoctonus* Brauns

1. Forewing vein cu-a reaching M+Cu distal of Rs+M; scutellar carina extending entire length of scutellum.....*S. narendrani* Soumya and Sudheer sp. n.
- Forewing vein cu-a reaching M+Cu proximal or opposite of Rs+M; scutellar carina not extending entire length of scutellum.....2
2. Forewing with Rs+2r strongly curved at proximal 0.3 to join pterostigma; glabrous area in anterior corner of discosubmarginal cell large; 1m-cu evenly arcuate.....*S. townesorum* Gauld and Mitchell

- Forewing with Rs+2r abruptly angled at proximal 0.1 to join pterostigma; glabrous area in anterior corner of discosubmarginal cell moderately small; 1m-cu sinuous.....**3**
- 3. Forewing vein cu-a reaching M+Cu usually proximal of Rs+M by up to 0.2 times its own length; cu-a subvertical; CI = 0.50-0.70; AI = 0.60-0.70.....*S. bombycivorus* (Gravenhorst)
- Forewing vein cu-a reaching M+Cu opposite of Rs+M; cu-a oblique; CI = 0.85-1.10; AI = 0.80-0.90.....*S. torresi* Gauld

Stauropoctonus narendrani Soumya and Sudheer sp. n.
(Figs. 1-12)

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Material examined: **Holotype:** Female. India: Kerala, Kannur district, Kannavam (11° 50'35''N 75°39'48''E), 12.ix.2021, Coll. Soumya T.K, Reg. No. NBRL 198.

Description: Body length: 28 mm.

Head: Antennae with 65 flagellar segments; antenna very long and slender; first flagellar segment 4.5x as long as wide and 2x as long as second flagellomere, 20th segment 1.8x as long as broad; lower face 0.6x as broad as long, entirely covered with punctures and polished with setae (Fig. 5); clypeus 1.9x as wide as high, moderately convex in profile, punctate; malar space 0.3x as long as basal width of mandible; mandible moderately long, twisted about 90°, outer surface with a diagonal groove (Fig. 5), mandibular teeth subequal; occipital carina absent; gena behind eye constricted; posterior ocellus very close to orbit (Fig. 3); FI = 0.65, GOI = 3.78.

Mesosoma: Moderately polished, entirely covered with hairs; pronotum polished with fine punctures and hairs; mesoscutum elongate, densely punctate with hairs; notauli absent; mesoscutum 1.3x as long as its maximum width in dorsal view; scutellum weakly convex with lateral longitudinal carinae extending entire length of scutellum (Fig. 6); epicnemium striato-punctate; epicnemial carina present, its upper end not reaching anterior margin of mesopleuron (Fig. 7); mesopleuron polished with punctures and hairs; mesopleural furrow well developed (Fig. 7); submetapleural carina present; metapleuron

moderately polished and covered with hairs, anterior half punctate, posterior half transversely striate; propodeum with anterior transverse carina complete; posterior area with transverse carina and sculptures as in figure (Fig. 8); posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete.

Wings: FWL = 21 mm; FWW = 5.10 mm; AI = 0.68; CI = 1; DI = 0.43; ICI = 0.91; SDI = 0.80; SI = 0.15; SRI = 0.28; vein 1m-cu sinuous without a ramellus; glabrous area in anterior corner of discosubmarginal cell extending 0.3x of length of Rs+2r (Fig. 10); proximal part of Rs+2r moderately geniculate, cu-a distal to base of Rs+M by 0.20x its own length (Fig. 10); posterior distal corner of second discal cell is 90°; posterior distal corner of subbasal cell 70°. HWL = 11.30 mm; HWW = 3.40 mm; NI = 1.07; Hind wing R1 with 13 hamuli of similar size and shape (Fig. 12).

Legs: Fore tibia without obvious spines on outer surface; fore tibial spur without trace of membranous flange behind microtrichial comb; distal margin of mid and hind trochantelli with acute curved tooth; hind coxa in profile 2.1x as long as wide; hind femur 0.6x as long as tibia; hind tarsal claw with distal pecten not projecting beyond apical tooth.

Metasoma: Metasoma polished, entirely covered with setae, long and slender with thyridia small, oval, separated from anterior margin of tergite by 3.4x its own length; anterior margin of second sternite behind level of petiolar spiracles (Fig. 9). DMI = 1.32; LMI = 4.89; PI = 2.6.

Colour: Yellowish to reddish brown species except for inter-ocellar area, apex of mandible and three longitudinal vitae of mesoscutum black; wings slightly infumate except for glabrous area of discosubmarginal cell hyaline; pterostigma and forewing vein Rs+2r light brown; fore, middle and hind leg yellowish to reddish brown; dorsal half of T3 and entire part of T5-8 and S5-8 are dark brown.

Male: Unknown. **Host:** Unknown.

Distribution: India: Kerala.

Etymology: The species is named after late Prof. T.C. Narendran for his contribution to the systematics of Indian Parasitic wasps.

Figures 1-11. *Stauropoctonus narendrani* sp. n. Holotype ♀: **1.** Habitus lateral view; **2.** Head frontal view; **3.** Head dorsal view; **4.** Head lateral view; **5.** Mandible; **6.** Scutellum; **7.** Mesosoma lateral view; **8.** Propodeum dorsal view; **9.** Metasoma lateral view; **10.** Forewing; **11.** Hindwing; **12.** Hindwing Hamuli.

Discussion

The new species *S. narendrani* sp. n. closely resembles *S. bombycivorus* (Gravenhorst) but differs from *S. bombycivorus* in having forewing vein cu-a reaching M+ Cu distal of Rs+M by up to 0.2x its own length (vs forewing vein cu-a reaching M+Cu proximal of Rs+M by upto 0.2x its own length); scutellum with lateral longitudinal carinae extending entire length of scutellum (vs lateral longitudinal carinae of scutellum extending to 0.2x length of scutellum); glabrous area in anterior corner of discosubmarginal cell extending 0.3x of length of Rs+2r (vs extending 0.1x of length of Rs+2r); hindcoxa, femur and tibia yellowish to reddish brown in colour (vs blackish); antennae with 65 segments (vs 70-76 segments); NI=1.07 (vs 0.7-0.9); SRI= 0.28 (vs 0.4); GOI= 3.7 (vs 2.5-3.0).

The new species closely resembles to the Japanese species *S. infuscus* (Uchida, 1928) in having forewing vein Cu-a reaching M+Cu distal to Rs+M by upto 0.2 times its own length; epicnemial carina strong laterally; forewing vein 1m-cu sinuate. However, *S. narendrani* sp. n. differs from *S. infuscus* in having the vein R1 with 13 hamuli (vs 10-12 hamuli); mandible twisted about 90° (vs 50-60°); FWL= 21 mm (vs 17 mm); DI = 0.4 (vs 0.6).

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